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Title: Valuing the feeling of safety: a willingness to pay experiment

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Objective

Early warning systems for infectious diseases and foodborne outbreaks are designed with the aim to increase the safety of citizens. To determine whether investing in such a system is worth the cost, a monetary value for the non-market good 'safety' needs to be obtained.

Methods

This study used contingent valuation to estimate people's willingness to pay (WTP) for increased safety due to an early warning system. For that purpose, eight different valuation scenarios involving various degrees of risk reduction and disease severity were developed. The contingent valuation experiment was administered to a cross-sectional, representative sample of UK citizens aged 18 to 65 (N=553) using an online questionnaire in February 2018. Regression analysis was conducted to investigate determinants of WTP valuations.

Results

Mean WTP per month for an early warning system was £20.5 (median £7) per household in the base scenario, in which neither risk reduction nor disease consequences were specified. In the scenario with a reduction from 4 to 2 % in the yearly risk of becoming infected by a health deteriorating disease, the mean WTP was £ 21.8 (median £7.5). Further scenarios showed that higher relative and absolute risk reductions and preventing more severe diseases were associated with higher WTP valuations. However, the change in WTP was not proportional, exemplified by a mean WTP of £33.0 (median £11) in a scenario with a reduction in the risk of getting infected with a deadly disease from 60 to 20%. Regression results indicate that overall, WTP valuations increased with household income, awareness of the risk of outbreaks and level of risk aversion of respondents.

Discussion

The results suggest that there is a quantifiable monetary value for safety in the context of an early warning system for infectious diseases and foodborne outbreaks.